

Zinc mediated ring size tuned C=C reduction and C-C coupling of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cycloalkanones

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Abstract : Reduction of substituted α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cycloalkanones bearing five- and six-membered rings using zinc-amalgam in glacial acetic acid yielded C=C bond reduced products and C-C coupled compounds with the carbonyl functions remaining unaffected. Ring conformation exerted pronounced influence on the extent of reduction. The diastereomerism around the coupled benzylic carbons and the relative orientations of the like groups varied with the central cycloalkanone ring types. DFT studies indicated conformational differences between the substrates of two cyclic systems and consequently the ease of electron transfer from metal to them would vary. Dimeric molecules exhibited their associative properties involving π - π interactions and intermolecular H-bond formation.

Keywords : Zinc-mediated reduction of C=C, C-C coupling, diastereomerism, DFT studies, molecular associativity.

Introduction

Various methodologies are known for the reduction of conjugated carbonyl compounds leading to the formation of a range of products following different mechanistic pathways. Of them, dissolving metal reduction involving electron transfer (SET) from metal to unsaturated system is unique since this process generates a radical ion which also undergoes C-C coupling. Amalgamated zinc in presence of moderately concentrated hydrochloric acid deoxygenates carbonyl functions to methylene groups, when pinacols, which are essentially intermolecular carbon-carbon coupled products, are also obtained¹⁻³. Extent of pre-treatment of zinc with mercuric chloride influences the nature and yield of the products. It is suggested that reduction steps follow either of the two different pathways - a carbanion intermediate^{4,5} or a zinc-carbenoid intermediate⁶. To widen the applicability of the reaction, several variations in the methodology were attempted viz. replacing hydrochloric acid with organic acids⁷, using hydrogen chloride in presence of acetic anhydride in dry ether^{8,9} and even trimethylchlorosilane^{10,11} as a substitute for proton etc. Following this methodology either both groups of α,β -unsaturated ketones were reduced or

only the olefinic bond had undergone reduction^{12,13}. In some cases coupled and rearranged compounds were isolated^{12,14-18}. Zinc mediated cyclodimerisation of α,β -unsaturated aromatic ketones in presence of mercuric chloride as Lewis acid catalyst was reported^{19,20}. Clemmensen reduction applied to 1,2-dibenzoylcycloalkanes yielded products depending on ring sizes of the substrate²¹. Reduction of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cycloalkanones possessing two exocyclic olefinic bonds remaining cross-conjugated to each other around the cyclic ketone functions involving SET had not been studied yet. It was envisaged that variations in ring sizes of these derivatives would produce subtle differences in planarity in their molecular architecture. This conjecture was confirmed from the DFT energy optimization studies of both α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanone (**1a**) and α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanone (**4a**) using B3LYP/6-31G basis set which showed that **4a** was more stable by 24657.9 kcal/mole with respect to **1a**. DFT presentation of **1a** indicated planar structure of the molecule since the dihedral angle (ϕ) for both exocyclic olefinic bonds with five-membered cyclic ketone function was found to be 0° and two phenyl rings of benzylidene groups participated

effectively in extending delocalization, whereas in case of **4a** bearing six-membered ring ketone, one exocyclic olefinic bond remained out of plane ($\varphi = 4^\circ$) with the conjugated system at the other end of the molecule.

coupled dimers **3a** and **6a** with olefinic bond reduction products **2a** and **5a**. The average combined yields of the two types of products for each substrate were $\sim 50\%$ with simultaneous isolation of gummy polymeric sub-

Fig. 1. Dihedral angle of compound **1a** and **4a** from DFT calculations.

We had studied the reduction of substituted α, α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene) derivatives of cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone with zinc-amalgam in glacial acetic acid and the results presented here indicated influences exerted by the sizes of central cyclic ketone functions.

Results and discussion

Reductions of α, α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)-cyclopentanone (**1a**) and α, α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)-cyclohexanone (**4a**) were carried out with variations in Zn : Hg ratio and the concentration of the substrates in glacial acetic acid with dry toluene as co-solvent under refluxing conditions to identify optimized conditions for cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone derivatives and the results were shown in Table 1 which identified that entries 2 and 7 might be suitable conditions for **1a** and **4a** respectively to obtain better yields of corresponding β, β' -

stances ($\sim 20\%$). However, for the entries 1 and 6, most of the starting materials were recovered. Extending reaction hours for either type of substrates did not change the composition of the products. Formation of polymeric materials was attributed to the tendency of initially formed benzyl radicals to undergo various side reactions. These results revealed several important features. Transformation of carbonyl functions to methylene groups were not observed for either substrate. The reaction time for **4a** was found to be less than in case of **3a** and the reduction patterns for two compounds were different.

Interestingly when each of the α, α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones **1a-c** and α, α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanones **4a-d** was subjected to zinc-mediated reductions following the respective optimized conditions as identified in Table 1, reaction times

Table 1. Optimization of the substrate concentration and zinc amalgam ratio for reduction

Entry	Zn : Hg	Substrate	Reaction time (h)	Mole taken in 300 ml toluene	Monomeric product	(%) yield	Coupled product	(%) yield
1	70 : 1	1a	2.0	0.20	2a	8	3a	3
2	80 : 1	1a	2.0	0.20	2a	32	3a	20
3	80 : 1	1a	2.0	0.10	2a	39	3a	9
4	80 : 1	1a	2.0	0.05	2a	47	3a	3
5	90 : 1	1a	2.0	0.20	2a	41	3a	11
6	70 : 1	4a	1.5	0.20	5a	7	6a	3
7	80 : 1	4a	1.5	0.20	5a	32	6a	19
8	80 : 1	4a	1.5	0.10	5a	35	6a	11
9	80 : 1	4a	1.5	0.05	5a	47	6a	2
10	90 : 1	4a	1.5	0.20	5a	43	6a	7

shown in Tables 2 and 3 indicated that substituent on the aromatic ring lowered the rate of reduction. Combined yields of the two products from both types of substrates were found comparable except for cyclohexanone derivatives **4c** and **4d** (entries 3 and 4 in Table 3). The latter observations could be rationalized on the basis of the conjugative effects and steric factors of the *p*-methyl and *p*-methoxy substituents. The structures of the products were deduced from their respective ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra along with the two-dimensional NMR (COSY, HSQC and HMBC *etc.*) experiments and mass spectral studies.

two exocyclic olefinic bonds on the cyclopentanone ring to give **2a-c** whereas reduced cyclohexanone derivatives **5a-d**, as indicated from their respective ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data, possessed an σ -plane passing through the carbonyl group and C-4 carbon of cyclohexanone ring with energetically favorable β -equatorial orientations of the two benzyl substituents derived from the reductions of both benzylidene groups at C-2 and C-6. The compounds **2a-c** and **5a-d** were synthesized earlier²²⁻²⁵ following different methodologies but not utilizing any zinc mediated reduction involving electron transfer process which we report here.

Table 2. Zinc-amalgam/acetic acid reduction products of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones

Entry	Starting material	Reaction time (h)	Products	Yield (%)
1		2a : 32		
				3a : 20
2		2b : 34		
				3b : 22
3		2c : 32		
				3c : 21

It was clear from Tables 2 and 3 that the structures assigned to the monomeric reduction products **2a-c** obtained from respective α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)-cyclopentanones **1a-c** were different from the structures elucidated for reduction products **5a-d** from corresponding cyclohexanone derivatives **4a-d**. In cases of **1a-c**, spectral data confirmed the reduction of only one of the

Scheme 1 indicated plausible mechanistic pathway for the reduction of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)-cycloalkanes. Reduction of both exocyclic olefinic bonds for α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanones **4a-d** could be suggested to occur in stepwise manner. Electron transfer from zinc surface to the conjugated β -benzylic carbon formed the stable benzyl radical **8** enjoying delocaliza-

Table 3. Zinc-amalgam/acetic acid reduction products of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones

Entry	Starting material	Reaction time (h)	Products	Yield (%)	
1	 7a : 32				
				 7a : —	
2	 7b : 5				
				 7b : 40	
3	 7c : 12				
				 7c : 12	
4	 7d : 38				
				 7d : 12	

Scheme 1. Mechanism for the reduction of α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones.

tion from one phenyl ring to the other. This radical would accept another electron from zinc to form the benzyl anion which would ultimately be quenched with proton from the acid present in medium to form the monomeric reduced products where one exocyclic bond was reduced leaving behind a conjugated enone function at the other end of the molecule. Reduction of the second olefinic bond would follow the same sequence of steps. C-C coupling between two radicals **8** yielded the reductive dimers. The partially reduced cyclohexanone derivative designated as **9** was not isolated during this reaction. It was also observed that **2a** was not reduced further to 2,5-dibenzylcyclopentanone designated as **10**. DFT calculations for the structures **2a**, **9** and **10** were carried out. Energy minimized structure of hypothetical molecule **10** was found more stable than **2a** by 761.23 kcal/mole. DFT analyses also revealed that the structure **2a** was less stable than the structure representing **9** by the energy 24659.64 kcal/mole. These data confirmed that ease of electron transfer from metal surface to the conjugated β -benzylic carbon was important for continuation of reduction steps and compound **2a** were somehow prevented from further electron transfer process from the metal surface. DFT structure of **2a** showed the co-planarity of exocyclic double bond with carbonyl function ($\varphi = 0^\circ$) of the cyclopentanone and participation of phenyl ring in this conjugation, whereas the DFT presentation of **9** indicated non-coplanarity ($\varphi = 16^\circ$) of the exocyclic double bond with six-membered cyclic keto group (shown in Fig. 2). Reluctance of **2a** to undergo further reduction via electron transfer from amalgamated zinc to conjugated β -benzylic carbon could be attributed to the possible steric hindrance towards proper orientation and interaction of the molecule with the metal surface.

The common feature of hitherto unreported β,β -coupled

dimers (Tables 2 and 3) from each of the α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones **1a-c** and α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanones **4a-d** was the presence of C_2 symmetry in their molecular framework as evidenced from their respective 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra and mass spectra. Compounds **1a-c** yielded corresponding dimeric products **3a-c** bearing similarities in their structural features. Presence of a reductive coupling between β -benzylic carbons was identified for each dimer and the conjugated keto functions at non-coupled ends of both monomeric units were retained. In the aliphatic region of the 1H NMR spectrum for the compound **3a**, the diastereomeric protons of two methylene carbons on cyclopentanone ring appeared as multiplets. The protons on allylic carbons (δ_C 27.4) resonated in the region δ 2.28–2.39 and 2.42–2.56. The latter multiplet also incorporated the signals for the proton on keto-methine carbon (δ_C 49.1). The resonance signals for other methylene (δ_C 25.8) protons were discernible at around δ 1.55–1.68 and 1.94–2.06. The benzylic-methine proton on carbon (δ_C 49.7) involved in coupling was, however, observed as a singlet at δ 4.36. The resonance signals of β -olefinic proton of α,β -unsaturated ketone system merged with the aromatic proton signals in the region δ 7.2–7.5. However, the structures elucidated for the coupled products from **4a-d** indicated differences in their reduction pattern. α,α' -(*E,E*)-Bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanone (**4a**) yielded **6a** as reductive dimer with a C-C bond between two β -benzylic carbons and the remaining exocyclic benzylidene groups on the monomers were further reduced to saturated benzyl groups. The 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound **6a** along with its COSY, HSQC and HMBC experiments showed signals for four methylene carbons at δ_C 25.4, 35.1, 35.3 and 36.3 bearing eight diastereomeric protons, indicated as pairs, at around δ

Fig. 2. Dihedral angle of compound **2a** and **9** from DFT calculations.

Fig. 3. X-Ray crystal structure of compound 3a.

1.54–1.64 and 1.78–1.88, δ 2.27 (dd, J_1 6.7 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz) and 3.05 (dd, J_1 6.4 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), δ 1.25–1.33 and 2.38–2.48, δ 1.30–1.36 and 1.96–2.08, respectively. The chemical shifts for three methine carbons were identified as δ_C 46.5, 53.4 and 54.2 and the corresponding protons resonated around δ 3.51–3.56, 2.65–2.75 and 2.38–2.48, respectively. The signals at δ_C 35.1 (CH₂) and 46.5 (CH) were assigned to benzylic carbons, the former being obtained from the reduction of the exocyclic olefinic bond of the non-coupled end of each monomeric unit and the latter being utilized for the coupling of monomers. The multiplet at δ 7.00–7.21 was attributed to aromatic protons (10Ar-H). The cyclohexanone derivative **4b**, which is 4-chloro analogue of **4a**, under similar reduction condition furnished two dimeric products **6b** and **7b**, the former being obtained in minor amount and found structurally same with **6a** whereas the reduction pattern observed in case of **7b** included usual β,β -benzylic coupling at one end of the molecule and the enone function in the constituent monomers remained unaffected. The other substrates viz. α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(4-methylbenzylidene)cyclohexanone **4c** and α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(4-methoxybenzylidene)cyclohexanone **4d** yielded respective β,β -coupled compounds **7c** and **7d** which showed structural resemblance with **7b**. When each of the dimeric products **7c-d** was subjected to further reduction, no change was observed.

To establish the nature of diastereomerism around the coupled benzylic carbons of these C₂-symmetric dimers, single crystal X-ray diffraction analyses of the compound

3a obtained from α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanone (**1a**) and of the coupled products **6a** and **7d** from respective cyclohexanone derivatives **4a** and **4d** were undertaken. The X-ray data revealed that **3a** (Fig. 3) remained as *erythro* isomer in staggered form whereas both **6a** (Fig. 4) and **7d** (Fig. 5) existed in *threo* configuration possessing unusual relative orientations of like groups. It was found that smallest hydrogen atoms were in *anti* relationship to each other with larger identical groups in *gauche-butane* relationship between themselves. We undertook the DFT calculations with the help of Gaussian using basis set 6-31G for the molecule **6a** and its conformer **6a'** having the hydrogen atoms in *gauche-butane* relationship between them. It was found that **6a** was of lower energy between the two conformers (Fig. 6).

Variations in the mode of C–C coupling and extent of reduction for two types of dimers observed could be cor-

Fig. 4. X-Ray crystal structure of compound 6a.

Fig. 5. X-Ray crystal structure of compound 7d.

Calculation was done with the help of Gaussian using basis set 6-31G

Fig. 6. Energy variation between the two conformers of 6a using DFT calculations.

related to the differences in the structural features of the substituted α, α' -(*E, E*)-bis-benzylidenes of two cyclic ketones. Lewis *et al.*²⁶ reported that monobenzylidene derivative of (+) camphor on treatment with sodium in refluxing toluene in presence of trimethylchlorosilane

yielded two β, β -coupled reductive dimers differing in the mode of coupling between the two benzylic carbons. The nature of coupling patterns and the relative orientations of the like groups in those two dimers were found to be identical with our results for cyclopentanone and cyclo-

hexanone derivatives. Incidentally both six-membered and five-membered ring ketone structural features were embedded within the bicyclic framework of camphor molecule. From our experimental data it became evident that the radical-ion derived from benzylidene derivative of five-membered ring ketone would always undergo different β,β -benzylic coupling with respect to its counterpart possessing six-membered ring ketone structure.

A π - π interaction between two phenyl rings was found in the unit cell of **6a** (Fig. 7). Interestingly, the dimers **6a** and **4a** derived from cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone derivatives respectively had shown molecular associativity (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8) involving intermolecular H-bonding. The measured distance of hydrogen bonding (CH \cdots O distance : 2.68 Å) and π -stacking (CH $\cdots\pi_m$ distance : 3.82 Å) of **6a** revealed that the corresponding binding forces are quite strong.

These weak non-covalent interactions are extremely useful in understanding chemical, biological and material phenomena²⁷⁻³². Presence of strong intermolecular weak binding interactions had prompted us to study the self-aggregation²⁸⁻³² property of **6a**. In fact, it formed spherical self-assembled materials on slow evaporation in acetone. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) imaging of the

materials revealed that the dimension of the sphere was in the range 2–4 micron (Fig. 9).

Conclusion :

Zinc mediated reduction of substituted α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclopentanones and α,α' -(*E,E*)-bis(benzylidene)cyclohexanones produced exocyclic olefinic bond reduced compounds and corresponding β,β -coupled dimers with varied extent of reductions and different modes of C-C coupling. DFT calculations of substrates and products correlated these observations with the subtle differences in the conformational features of the substrates and possible reaction intermediates and also the ease of electron transfer to them from metal surface.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes on Kofler block apparatus and are uncorrected. Chromatography columns were prepared from silica gel (100–200 mesh; Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., India). IR spectra were recorded in cm^{-1} using KBr discs with a Perkin-Elmer RXI FTIR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (^1H , ^{13}C , COSY, NOESY/ROESY, HMBC, HSQC) were recorded in CDCl_3 solution in 5 mm BBO probe fitted with a pulse field gradient and working with Topsin 1.3 programme

Fig. 7. Association through intermolecular H-bonding and π - π interaction of compound **6a**.

Fig. 8. Association through intermolecular H-bonding of compound 4a.

Fig. 9. Scanning electron microscope image of the self-aggregated material of 6a.

in a Bruker AV-300 Supercon NMR spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm and J in Hz). Mass spectrometry was performed on a Qtof Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer. X-Ray crystallographic data were taken on a Bruker Smart Apex 2 diffractometer equipped with a CCD area detector with graphite monochromatized Mo K_{α} radiation. Further information on the crystal structure investigations may be obtained from Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK, fax +44-(0)1223-336033 or email : (deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk) on quoting the depository numbers 787520 for $C_{38}H_{34}O_2$ (3a), 787522 for $C_{40}H_{42}O_2$

(6a) and 787521 for $C_{44}H_{46}O_6$ (7d).

Reaction procedure :

Distilled glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and zinc amalgam (0.39 mol, zinc-mercury ratio 80 : 1) were added to α, α' -bisarylidencycloalkanones (0.02 mol) dissolved in dry toluene (300 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h. Then the cooled reaction mixture was filtered and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue left was washed 2–3 times with toluene and resolved by chromatography over a column of silica gel by eluting with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture of increasing polarity.

(E)-2-Benzyl-5-benzylidenecyclopentanone (**2a**) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 116–118 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1706, 1622, 751, 693; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.56–1.70 (1H, m), 2.15–2.26 (1H, m), 2.59–2.69 (2H, m), 2.72–2.85 (1H, m), 2.94–3.05 (1H, m), 3.36 (1H, d, J 9.7 Hz), 7.25–7.59 (10Ar-H and 1 olefinic H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 26.6, 27.3, 36.0 (3 CH_2), 50.2 (1CH), 126.0, 128.3 ($\times 2$), 128.6 ($\times 2$), 128.8 ($\times 2$), 129.2, 130.4 ($\times 2$), 132.7 (11CH), 135.4, 136.0, 139.9 (3C), 207.6 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 285.01, calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{ONa}$ 285.13.

(E)-2-(4-Chlorobenzyl)-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-cyclopentanone (**2b**) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 159–160 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1706, 1620, 1487; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.50–1.65 (1H, m), 2.10–2.25 (1H, m), 2.55–2.65 (2H, m), 2.68–2.80 (1H, m), 2.85–2.99 (1H, m), 3.25 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz), 7.15 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.25 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 7.37–7.39 (2Ar-H and 1 olefinic H, m), 7.45 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 26.5, 27.3, 35.3 (3 CH_2), 50.0 (CH), 128.5 ($\times 2$), 128.9 ($\times 2$), 130.3 ($\times 2$), 131.6 ($\times 3$) (9CH), 132.0, 133.9, 135.3, 136.3, 138.2 (5C), 207.2 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 353.16, calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{Cl}_2\text{ONa}$ 353.06.

(E)-2-(4-Methylbenzyl)-5-(4-methylbenzylidene)-cyclopentanone (**2c**) :

Pale yellow cubic crystal, m.p. 84 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3016, 2923, 2863, 1701, 1618; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.55–1.65 (1H, m), 2.10–2.20 (1H, m), 2.32 (3H, s), 2.37 (3H, s), 2.50–2.62 (2H, m), 2.70–2.80 (1H, m), 2.88–2.98 (1H, m), 3.24–3.30 (1H, m), 7.10 (4Ar-H, s), 7.21 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.43 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.1 Hz and 1 olefinic H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 20.9, 21.4 (2 CH_3), 26.6, 27.4, 35.6 (3 CH_2), 50.3 (1CH), 128.8 ($\times 2$), 129.0 ($\times 2$), 129.4 ($\times 2$), 130.5 ($\times 2$), 132.7 (9CH), 132.8, 135.1, 135.5, 136.9, 139.6 (5C), 207.9 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 313.26, calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{ONa}$ 313.16.

(2E,2'E)-5,5'-(1,2-Diphenylethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-benzylidenecyclopentanones) (**3a**) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 238–240 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1704, 1617, 756, 694; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.55–1.68 (1H, m), 1.94–2.06 (1H,

m), 2.28–2.39 (1H, m), 2.42–2.56 (2H, m), 4.36 (1H, s), 7.20–7.50 (10Ar-H and 1 olefinic H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 25.8, 27.4 (2 CH_2), 49.1, 49.7 (2CH), 126.7, 128.3 ($\times 2$), 128.5 ($\times 3$), 129.0, 130.3 ($\times 3$), 131.4 (11CH), 135.6, 137.9, 141.4 (3C), 208.9 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 545.01, calculated for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$ 545.26.

(2E,2'E)-5,5'-(1,2-Bis(4-chlorophenyl)ethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-(4-chlorobenzylidene)cyclopentanones) (**3b**) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 220–222 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2938, 1711, 1623, 1488; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.5–1.65 (1H, m), 1.97–2.07 (1H, m), 2.36–2.54 (3H, m), 4.32 (1H, s), 7.23–7.30 (6Ar-H and 1 olefinic H, m), 7.41 (2Ar-H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 25.4, 27.2 (2 CH_2), 48.7, 49.7 (2CH), 128.6, 128.8 ($\times 3$), 130.6 ($\times 2$), 131.5 ($\times 3$) (9CH), 132.7, 133.7, 135.2, 137.8, 139.6 (5C), 208.1 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 681.0830, calculated for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{30}\text{Cl}_4\text{O}_2\text{Na}$ 681.0898.

(2E,2'F)-5,5'-(1,2-Di-*p*-tolylethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-(4-methylbenzylidene)cyclopentanones) (**3c**) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 224–226 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2933, 1703, 1617; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.50–1.67 (1H, m), 1.91–2.05 (1H, m), 2.17 (3H, s), 2.26 (3H, s), 2.32–2.52 (3H, m), 4.29 (1H, s), 7.06 (2Ar-H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.10–7.17 (3Ar-H, m), 7.23–7.28 (1Ar-H and 1 olefinic H, m), 7.37 (2H, d, J 7.9 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 21.0, 21.3 (2 CH_3), 25.7, 27.4 (2 CH_2), 49.1, 49.3 (2CH), 129.0 ($\times 2$), 129.2 ($\times 3$), 130.4 ($\times 3$), 131.2 (9CH), 132.9, 136.0, 137.1, 138.5, 139.2 (5C), 209.0 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 601.3074, calculated for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$ 601.3083.

2,6-Dibenzylcyclohexanone (**5a**) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 111 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3023, 2928, 2859, 1687, 744, 691; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.33–1.48 (2H, m), 1.52–1.68 (1H, m), 1.78–1.87 (1H, m), 2.13 (2H, d, J 12.9 Hz), 2.52 (2H, dd, J_1 8.7 Hz, J_2 13.7 Hz), 2.60–2.71 (2H, m), 3.34 (2H, dd, J_1 4.5 Hz, J_2 13.7 Hz), 7.2–7.4 (10Ar-H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 25.1, 34.6 ($\times 2$), 35.3 ($\times 2$) (5 CH_2), 52.6 (2CH), 125.7 ($\times 2$), 128.1 ($\times 4$), 129.0 ($\times 4$) (10CH), 140.4 ($\times 2$) (2C), 212.4 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found

301.1591, calculated for C₂₀H₂₂ONa 301.1569.

2,6-Bis(4-chlorobenzyl)cyclohexanone (5b) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 122 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2932, 2859, 1694, 1486, 1447; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.33 (2H, dq, J_1 3.5 Hz, J_2 12.9 Hz), 1.57 (1H, tq, J_1 3.4 Hz, J_2 13.4 Hz), 1.75–1.85 (1H, m), 2.04 (2H, dd, J_1 2.6, J_2 13.1 Hz), 2.41 (2H, dd, J_1 8.2 Hz, J_2 12.8 Hz), 2.48–2.59 (2H, m), 3.17 (2H, dd, J_1 4.9 Hz, J_2 13.7 Hz), 7.01 (4H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.24 (4H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 25.2, 34.7 (×2), 34.8 (×2) (5CH₂), 52.7 (2CH), 128.3 (×4), 130.4 (×4) (8CH), 131.7 (×2), 138.9 (×2) (4C), 212.7 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 369.14, calculated for C₂₀H₂₀Cl₂ONa 369.08.

2,6-Bis(4-methylbenzyl)cyclohexanone (5c) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 106–108 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2929, 1698, 1509, 1444; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.23–1.40 (2H, m), 1.45–1.58 (1H, m), 1.65–1.76 (1H, m), 1.98–2.06 (2H, m), 2.30 (6H, s), 2.33–2.41 (2H, dd, J_1 8.7 Hz, J_2 13.8 Hz), 2.47–2.56 (2H, m), 3.18 (2H, dd, J_1 4.8 Hz, J_2 13.8 Hz), 7.01–7.08 (8Ar-H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 20.9 (×2) (2CH₃), 25.3, 34.7 (×2), 34.9 (×2) (5CH₂), 52.9 (×2) (2CH), 128.8 (×4), 128.9 (×4) (8Ar-CH), 135.2 (×2), 137.4 (×2) (4C), 212.8 (C=O). LCMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 329.29, calculated for C₂₂H₂₆ONa 329.19.

2,6-Bis(4-methoxybenzyl)cyclohexanone (5d) :

Colorless needle shaped crystal, m.p. 156–158 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2929, 1689, 1610, 1510; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.32 (2H, dq, J_1 3.5 Hz, J_2 12.8 Hz), 1.46–1.62 (1H, m), 1.72–1.82 (1H, m), 2.05 (2H, dd, J_1 2.5 Hz, J_2 13.1 Hz), 2.36 (2H, dd, J_1 8.5 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), 2.45–2.58 (2H, m), 3.16 (2H, dd, J_1 4.7 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), 3.77 (6H, s), 6.81 (4Ar-H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 7.07 (4Ar-H, d, J 8.7 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 25.3, 34.5 (×2), 34.9 (×2) (5CH₂), 53.1 (×2) (2CH), 55.2 (×2) (2CH₃), 113.7 (×4), 130.0 (×4) (8CH), 132.6 (×2), 157.8 (×2) (4C), 213.0 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 361.1700, calculated for C₂₂H₂₆O₃Na 361.1780.

2-Benzyl-6-(2-(3-benzyl-2-oxocyclohexyl)-1,2-diphenylethyl)cyclohexanone (6a) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 158–160 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2935, 1708, 1595, 754, 699; ¹H NMR (300 MHz,

CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.25–1.36 (2H, m), 1.54–1.64 (1H, m), 1.78–1.88 (1H, m), 1.96–2.08 (1H, m), 2.27 (1H, dd, J_1 6.7 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), 2.38–2.48 (2H, m), 2.65–2.75 (1H, m), 3.05 (1H, dd, J_1 6.4 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), 3.51–3.56 (1H, m), 7.00–7.21 (10Ar-H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 25.4, 35.1, 35.3, 36.3 (4CH₂), 46.5, 53.4, 54.2 (3CH), 125.7 (×2), 127.3 (×2), 128.1 (×2), 128.8 (×2), 129.6 (×2) (10CH), 140.7, 141.2 (2C), 213.4 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 577.3095, calculated for C₄₀H₄₂O₂Na 577.3083.

2-(4-Chlorobenzyl)-6-(2-(3-(4-chlorobenzyl)-2-oxocyclohexyl)-1,2-bis(4-chlorophenyl)ethyl)cyclohexanone (6b) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 246 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2934, 1705, 1486; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 0.8–1.0 (1H, m), 1.06–1.20 (1H, m), 1.45–1.52 (1H, m), 1.54–1.74 (2H, m), 1.83–1.87 (1H, m), 1.96–2.09 (1H, m), 2.21 (1H, dd, J_1 5.7 Hz, J_2 13.9 Hz), 2.26–2.37 (1H, m), 2.94 (1H, dd, J_1 7.5 Hz, J_2 13.8 Hz), 3.65 (1H, s), 7.02 (4Ar-H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 7.25 (4Ar-H, d, J 8.3 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 25.5, 34.9, 35.1, 35.5 (4CH₂), 49.7, 52.2, 53.3 (3CH), 128.2 (4), 130.5 (4) (8CH), 131.5, 132.1, 139.1, 139.3 (4C), 212.6 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 713.1531, calculated for C₄₀H₃₈Cl₄O₂Na 713.1524.

(2E,2'E)-6,6'-(1,2-Bis(4-chlorophenyl)ethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-(4-chlorobenzylidene)cyclohexanone) (7E) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 192 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2936, 2859, 1683, 1600, 1488; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.25–1.38 (1H, m), 1.43–1.62 (1H, m), 1.66–1.79 (1H, m), 1.80–1.93 (1H, m), 2.04–2.24 (1H, m), 2.34 (1H, dd, J_1 6.2 Hz, J_2 11.8 Hz), 2.65 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 4.16 (1H, s), 7.12–7.43 (1 olefinic H and 8Ar-H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} : 22.8, 28.3, 28.9 (3CH₂), 50.1, 52.1 (2CH), 128.4 (×2), 128.5 (×3), 131.4 (×3), 134.1 (9CH), 132.5, 134.0, 134.4, 138.0, 139.8 (5C), 203.2 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z) : [M+Na]⁺ found 709.1284, calculated for C₄₀H₃₄Cl₄O₂Na 709.1211.

(2E,2'E)-6,6'-(1,2-Bi-p-tolylethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-(4-methylbenzylidene)cyclohexanone) (7c) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 202 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 2935, 1667, 1592, 1508; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} : 1.20–1.33 (1H, m), 1.57–1.70 (2H, m), 1.85–1.89 (1H, m), 2.09–2.26 (1H, m), 2.27 (3H, s), 2.32 (3H, s), 2.35–2.43 (1H, m), 2.62 (1H, d, J 15.5 Hz), 4.15 (1H, s), 7.03 (2Ar-H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.14 (4Ar-H and 1 olefinic

H, m), 7.32 (2Ar-H, d, J 7.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 20.9, 21.2 (2 CH_3), 22.8, 28.3, 28.4 (3 CH_2), 50.5, 52.1 (2CH), 128.7 ($\times 2$), 128.9 ($\times 3$), 130.2 ($\times 3$), 134.9 (9CH), 133.1, 135.9, 136.8, 138.2, 138.5 (5C), 203.5 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z): $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 629.3348, calculated for $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$ 629.3396.

(2*E*, 2'*E*)-6,6'-(1,2-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)ethane-1,2-diyl)bis(2-(4-methoxybenzylidene)cyclohexanone (7d) :

Colorless cubic crystal, m.p. 200 °C; IR ν_{max} (KBr) : 2935, 1665, 1580, 1507; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.58 (2H, br.s), 1.80 (1H, br.s), 2.11–2.13 (1H, m), 2.2–2.4 (1H, m), 2.82 (1H, d, J 16.5 Hz), 3.33 (1H, br.s), 3.67 (3H, s, twin peak), 3.80 (3H, s, twin peak), 3.85 (1H, br.s), 6.49–6.54 (2Ar-H, m), 6.85–6.92 (4Ar-H, m), 7.31–7.36 (2Ar-H, m), 7.47 (1H, br.s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 23.2, 28.6, 29.1 (3 CH_2), 50.3, 53.8 (2CH), 54.8, 55.2 (2 CH_3), 112.8 ($\times 2$), 113.8 ($\times 3$), 130.7, 132.2 ($\times 2$), 135.4 (9CH), 128.6, 134.4, 136.0, 157.4, 159.8 (5C), 205.1 (C=O). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z): $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ found 693.3186, calculated for $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$ 693.3192.

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